

A new rice cultivation technology: plastic film mulching

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Rice growing under plastic film mulching cultivation in Zhejiang, China, 1998

Growing lowland rice using plastic film mulch under nonflooded conditions was tested extensively in 1993 by the Agricultural Bureau of Shiyan, Hubei Province, China (Shen et al 1997b). This cultivation system has also been evaluated in Liaoning, Anhui, Zhejiang, and Jiangsu provinces. In the mountainous areas of Shiyan, rice yield is greatly limited by low temperature. Film mulching cultivation is one crop management option that effectively alleviates low-temperature stress on rice growth and consequently increases rice production. In some rice-growing areas of Anhui Province, water scarcity is the major constraint to rice production. Film mulching cultivation reduces irrigation water consumption and therefore increases rice production by extending rice-planting areas. In this mini review, we compared the major characteristics of film mulching cultivation with the continuously flooded rice system.

Plastic film mulching cultivation

In the plastic film mulching cultivation test in Shiyan, Hubei, China (Shen et al 1997a), land was first flooded and then plowed and puddled. During land preparation, N, P, and K fertilizers and farmyard manure were applied and incorporated in the soil. The field was drained and 1.6-m-wide beds were prepared before plastic film was installed. Plastic film, 0.005-mm-thick and 1.7-m-wide, was used to cover the beds. Rice seedlings were transplanted in seven rows in each bed at a spacing of 0.13×0.25 m with two seedlings per hill. During the growing season, foliar N was applied only when rice plants showed N deficiency. Furrow irrigation was done when the field was dry. In control plots without plastic film, the field was continuously flooded. Other crop management practices used were the same for both plastic film mulch and control plots.

Increasing soil temperature

The plastic film mulch preserves heat and increases soil temperature. Shen et al (1997b) reported that mulching increased the daily mean temperature of the soil surface by 3-6 °C and seasonal accumulative heat units by

430-450 °C. Nagata et al (1997) found that the temperature of the film surface in the mulched plot was 10.3 °C greater than that of the water surface in the control plot. In a pot study, Nagata et al (1994) observed that 0.02-mm-thick plastic film mulch increased soil temperature at a 3-cm depth by up to 5 °C during the day and by 1.5 °C at night.

Water conservation

Plastic film mulching cultivation saves water by reducing water consumption during land preparation and evaporation during the growing season. Shen et al (1997a) reported that water saved by mulching cultivation was 640 m³ ha⁻¹ before crop establishment and 450-600 m³ ha⁻¹ from reduced evaporation during the growing season. Compared with the continuously flooded system, plastic film mulch reduced water consumption by almost 50%. In plastic film mulching cultivation, water is often supplied by furrow irrigation. In some rice-growing areas of China, rainfall provides enough water for rice growth in the plastic film mulch system.

Improving fertilizer use efficiency

In the continuously flooded rice system, fertilizer N-use efficiency is low due to rapid losses of applied N through volatilization, percolation, runoff, and seepage. N losses through percolation and seepage are greatly reduced in plastic film mulching cultivation due to furrow irrigation. Increased soil temperature in plastic film mulching cultivation also contributes to greater nutrient uptake in low-temperature areas. Experiments conducted in Zhejiang Province indicated that plastic film mulching reduced fertilizer N input by 30-50% (Wu 1997, personal communication). It is unknown whether film mulching reduces N loss through volatilization to a greater extent than the continuously flooded system.

Weed control

Plastic film mulching probably controls weeds by reducing O₂ concentration in the layer between the soil and the film. Shen et al (1997a) reported 28 weed plants m⁻² with film mulching and 326 m⁻² in the control. Plastic film mulching reduces weeds by 90%; thus, there is no need to apply herbicides in this cultivation system.

Increasing rice yield

In rice-growing areas where air temperature is low, plastic film mulching cultivation increases rice grain yield. A maximum yield of 10.8 t ha⁻¹ under plastic film mulching cultivation or a 42% increase over the control was reported by Shen et al (1997a). In 1996, plastic film mulching cultivation was demonstrated in many farmers' fields in Shiyan (Shen et al 1997a). The average yield from 1,156 ha was 7.3 t ha⁻¹, a 19% increase over the control. Total growth duration was reduced by 5 d. The yield improvement was mainly due to increased panicle number per square meter because high temperature accelerated early tillering. Plastic film mulching cultivation produced larger and more vigorous root systems than those under the continuously flooded system (Shen et al 1997a). It is necessary to determine

whether plastic film mulching can increase grain yield under favorable rice-growing conditions.

Economic analysis

Plastic film mulching cultivation is economically acceptable to Chinese farmers because of the low costs of plastic film and labor. About 53 kg of plastic film was needed per hectare, which costs about US\$90. Plastic film mulching saved US\$25 ha⁻¹ from fertilizer N, US\$18 from herbicides, and US\$37 from manual weeding in Shiyan (Shen et al 1997b). The savings from irrigation water was not estimated because water was free in Shiyan. The cost for transplanting and film installation was estimated at US\$55 ha⁻¹. The increase in grain yield was 1.4 t ha⁻¹ averaged across 1,156 ha, which was equivalent to US\$268 ha⁻¹. Farmers' net income increased by US\$203 ha⁻¹.

Future outlook

Plastic film mulching cultivation is a promising technology for rice-growing areas where low temperature and water shortage limit rice production. It is also suitable for hybrid rice production because low-density planting and a single seedling per hill have been practiced in growing hybrid rice. The adoption of this technology largely depends on the cost of plastic film and labor costs for film installation and transplanting. Direct dibble seeding coupled with plastic film mulching has been tested in Zhejiang Province. A medium-size machine that can both lay the plastic film and direct seed would promote the extension of this technology.

Reduced fertilizer N losses and reduced herbicide application in plastic film mulching cultivation will minimize environmental pollution. Methane emission may also be reduced because of the aerobic condition and film covering. The used plastic film, however, is a potential threat to the environment if it is not removed from the field and if recycling is not properly practiced. Biodegradable plastic film will solve this problem if its price is affordable.

Future studies should focus on developing new varieties and a fertilizer management strategy suitable for this cultivation system. Short- and long-term changes in soil quality (soil chemistry and physics) due to plastic film mulching cultivation should be monitored and studied in the context of sustainability.

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